

Penetrating orbital injury causing a pre-pontine haemorrhage and abducens palsy

S Rashid, MD (KCMUCo); *Division of Neurosurgery, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa.*
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7871-3399>

B Kgaodi, MBBS (UB), FC Neurosurg (SA), Mmed Neurosurgery (UCT); *Department of Ophthalmology, Red Cross War Memorial Children's Hospital, Cape Town, South Africa*
<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0858-2336>

C Tinley, MBChB, FRCOphth (London); *Division of Ophthalmology, Groote Schuur Hospital, University of Cape Town, South Africa.*
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5817-7122>

N Enslin, BPhyT, MBChB (UP), MMed Neurosurgery (UCT), FC Neurosurg (SA); *Division of Neurosurgery, University of Cape Town, Neurosciences Institute, Red Cross War Memorial Children's Hospital, Cape Town, South Africa*
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6384-7781>

A Figaji, MBChB, MMed Neurosurgery (UCT), FC Neurosurg (SA), PhD, BPhyT, MBChB (UP), MMed Neurosurgery (UCT), FC Neurosurg (SA); *Division of Neurosurgery, University of Cape Town, Neurosciences Institute, Red Cross War Memorial Children's Hospital, Cape Town, South Africa*
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3357-6490>

Corresponding author: Sakina M Rashid, email: sakina.rashid@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Penetrating traumatic brain injury (TBI) in children is rare, but potentially fatal and is easily missed. We present an illustrative case of an 11-year-old female who sustained a potentially fatal penetrating orbital injury, which was missed at her index presentation. A sharp object was unintentionally thrust into her left eye, and she presented two days later with an abducens palsy that prompted a computed tomography (CT) scan of her brain. A small left pre-pontine hyperdensity was overlooked. Review at her routine follow-up prompted further magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

Results: MRI slices through the midbrain and posterior fossa clearly delineated the transorbital intracranial tract with brainstem penetration. Three-dimensional reconstruction of the images demonstrated trajectory through the left superior orbital fissure.

Conclusion: While penetrating orbital injuries may be obvious on initial presentation, the external signs of significant intracranial penetration can be subtle in children. Awareness of the risk is key to appropriate investigation. A thorough review of the presenting history, detailed neurological examination, and consideration of the involved anatomy reduces the chances of missed injury. With respect to transorbital injury, the conical shape of the orbit tends to direct penetrating objects towards high-risk anatomical regions.

Keywords: penetrating head injury, orbital trauma, abducens palsy, traumatic brain injury, children.

Funding: Not applicable.

Declarations: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Introduction

Trauma remains the leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide in older children and young adults. South Africa has a significant burden of trauma, with approximately 30 000 trauma related deaths annually.¹

Traumatic brain injuries (TBIs) are a common cause of poor outcomes: at one high volume provincial trauma centre, TBIs accounted for 32.7% of all trauma mortality; penetrating injuries had a 20% mortality overall.²

Penetrating brainstem injuries are often fatal.³ Survival following transorbital pontine injuries has been reported in literature; however, this is rare³ because of

the complex neural and vascular anatomy in a compact area.⁴

While penetrating TBIs are often obvious on presentation, because of the nature of the injury and the presence of open wounds and foreign material, patients may also present with occult injuries. This is most relevant to childhood injuries because the thinner scalp and bone protecting the central nervous system are more easily breached. Therefore, a high index of suspicion is needed to identify penetrating intracranial injury where the external manifestation is subtle.

This case illustrates the potential for high-risk intracranial injury with minimal external signs.

Statement of ethics

Informed consent and assent were obtained from the mother and the child respectively to proceed with writing and publishing this report. Every effort has been made to exclude information that may identify the child.

Case presentation History

An 11-year female was looking through a keyhole of a door, when her friend on the other side of the door forcefully directed a sharp thin object through the keyhole and unintentionally into her left orbit. She experienced immediate, severe pain in her left eye that settled over some time. On presentation two days later to our

hospital, she complained of headaches, diplopia, a weak left leg and three episodes of vomiting since the incident.

Examination

On examination, her Glasgow Coma Score (GCS) was 15/15. There was mild left periorbital swelling and a small subconjunctival haemorrhage. Examination of the extraocular movements showed a left sixth nerve palsy. There was no motor weakness noted on lower limb examination; however, proprioception was decreased in the left lower limb. The rest of her examination was unremarkable.

Initial imaging: Computed Tomography (CT) scan

During her index presentation, she underwent a CT scan of the head to assess the extent of her injury and to rule out any retained foreign material in the orbit. There was a hyperdensity anterior to the pons of the brainstem on the left

Figure 1: CTB demonstrating pre-pontine hyperdensity.

which was initially overlooked (Figure 1). The impression was a sixth nerve injury resulting in a medially deviated left eye. No foreign material was noted in the orbit.

Clinical course

Following her initial presentation, she was admitted for close observation to ensure there was no progression of her symptoms. After 48 hours she was discharged for regular out-patient follow-up. As there was no retained foreign material or any open wounds, no further interventions were instituted during the initial admission. A penetrating brain stem injury had not been considered initially, largely due to how well the child was, and the physical examination signs were thought to be explained by an isolated sixth cranial nerve injury.

During her first clinic follow-up, she

Figure 2: A – Primary position, B – Right gaze, C – Left gaze.

was reviewed, and the concern was raised that the subtle hyperdensity on the head CT scan represented subarachnoid blood or contusion, which implied that there was intracranial injury that needed further investigation. Re-examination of the extraocular movements showed a persistent left sixth nerve palsy (Figure 2). A magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scan was performed to delineate the extent of injury.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) findings

MRI of the brain three weeks post-injury showed a tract with old blood products that traversed the left lateral pons and the

Figure 3: Susceptibility Weighted Imaging (SWI) of the posterior fossa demonstrating the tract through the brain stem and cerebellum.

middle cerebellar peduncle, extending into the white matter tracts of the cerebellum (Figure 3). Also noted upon closer examination of the extraconal fat in the left eye was a region of hypodensity between the medial and inferior rectus muscles, which was the likely path of the sharp penetrating object. No false aneurysm was observed.

Clinical course – treatment and outcome

She was followed-up regularly in our outpatient service. The sixth nerve palsy completely resolved over the next few months.

Discussion

Penetrating head injuries are often obvious on initial presentation and rare in children. However, when they do occur, they can present as fatal incidences or with extremely subtle findings that are overlooked by the treating doctor. A combination of physical examination findings, potential trajectory of the penetrating object and radiographic findings can guide the diagnosis and further management of such injuries.

One such entry into the cranium is the orbital route. Sun *et al* reviewed the variety of everyday objects that have resulted in penetrating pontine injuries through the orbit. Survival is often accompanied by significant neurological fall out. The orbit is a high-risk area because it is a soft tissue corridor into the cranial vault, where its conical shape directs penetrating objects towards its apex and therefore, towards

the brainstem.

The sixth nerve has the longest path of any of the cranial nerves. Within the orbit, the sixth nerve innervates the lateral rectus muscle which abducts the eye and allows lateral gaze of the ipsilateral eye. MRI of the orbit in this case showed a hypodensity in the fat between the medial and inferior rectus muscle, away from the more lateral path of the sixth nerve within the orbit. If the sixth nerve was injured in the orbit, it is likely the injury was more proximal, as the nerve traversed the superior orbital fissure.

The second site of the sixth nerve that may have been injured by the projectile is within the cavernous sinus. It is the only cranial nerve that runs through the cavernous sinus that is not within the fold of dura forming its lateral wall. That could explain why an isolated sixth nerve palsy was noted with sparing of the third, fourth and fifth (V_1 and V_2) nerves. The internal carotid artery and its sympathetic plexus lie in close proximity to the sixth nerve in the cavernous sinus. The patient's examination excluded a Horner's syndrome or any neurological fall-out attributable to a carotid artery injury therefore further imaging to assess this was not undertaken. It should be noted however that a luminal injury of the carotid artery would place the patient at risk for pseudoaneurysms later in life.^{5,6}

As the sixth nerve runs up the clivus and over the petrous apex, it turns 90 degrees to enter Dorello's canal. The projectile may have scraped across the petroclinoid ligament and the sixth nerve prior to continuing its postero-inferior course into the brainstem at the level of the pons.

The MRI of the midbrain and posterior fossa demonstrate the path that the trajectory took, improved by the three-dimensional reconstruction of the images. It appears the likely point of the sixth nerve's injury was at the left superior orbital fissure (Figure 4). The reconstructed images also place into context how fortunate the child was not to have sustained injury to several critical neural and vascular structures in close proximity to the tract, including the basilar artery and its branches perfusing the brainstem (Figure 5).

The sixth nerve nucleus is spared, and the path is generally away from the sixth nerve fibres within the brainstem, being superior and lateral to the nucleus. However, it is not impossible to exclude local oedema or irritation due to subarachnoid blood. The patient's gradual recovery of the sixth nerve function

Figure 4: Bony reconstruction demonstrating the trajectory of the projectile.

indicates that it was likely a neuropraxia versus an axonotmesis or neurotmesis.

Fortunately, there was no vascular injury of the basilar artery or its branches, which could have led to a devastating outcome through haemorrhage immediately or delayed due to a false aneurysm.

Conclusion

Penetrating brain injury in children is easy to miss. Orbital entry is one such route where significant penetration into critical structures can occur with little external manifestation. A high index of suspicion, along with careful clinical and radiological evaluation, are key to not missing these injuries.

References

1. MRC/UNISA Crime, Violence and Injury Lead Programme. A profile of fatal injuries in South Africa 2008 - Annual Report for South Africa Based on National Injury Mortality Surveillance System (www.ac.za/crime/nimss07.PDF)
2. Moodley N B, Aldous C, Clarke DL (2014) An audit of trauma-related mortality in a provincial capital in South Africa. *S. Afr. J. Surg* 2014;52(4):101-104 DOI:10.7196/SAJS.1995.
4. MacLean MA, Mukhida K, Shankar JJ, Schmidt MH, Clarke DB (2019) Complete recovery following transorbital penetrating head injury traversing the brainstem: case report. *J Neurosurg Pediatr* 6;24(6):697-701. <https://doi.org/10.3171/2019.6.PEDS19106>.
4. Sun G, Yagmurlu K, Belykh E, Lei T, Preul MC (2016) Management strategy of a transorbital penetrating pontine injury by a wooden chopstick. *World Neurosurg* 1;95:622-e7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2014.11.002>
5. Alfawaz A, Li X, Kénel-Pierre S, Yang J, Rey J, Robinson H. Delayed presentation of a carotid pseudoaneurysm following penetrating neck trauma *SAGE Open Med Case Rep*. 2016 May.
6. Garg K, Rockman CB, Lee V, Maldonado TS, Jacobowitz GR, Adelman MA, Mussa FF. Presentation and management of carotid artery aneurysms and pseudoaneurysms. *J. Vasc. Surg.* 2012 Jun 1;55(6):1618-22.

Figure 5: Image reconstruction demonstrating critical neural and vascular structures in close proximity to the tract.